

Smart Cities 2035

Four scenarios on how emerging
technologies will shape our society

Authored by

In collaboration with

Executive Summary

This document aims to spread the outcome of a **future-oriented research project** centred around the development of possible future scenarios regarding the usage of data in medium-small Italian municipalities that adopt smart solutions.

The document opens with an overview of the research context – the Observatory on Trends and Applications of Supercomputing – in which this study is situated. Next, the theoretical foundations of the study are presented. Drawing from the field of Future Studies, this section clarifies the distinctions between forecasting, foresight, and anticipation, and explains the principles and objectives of strategic foresight.

The methodology section follows, detailing the diverse techniques employed to achieve the project's objectives. The research, that **involved a panel of visionary experts**, combined horizon scanning with scenario planning, allowing for a comprehensive exploration of trends, uncertainties, and transformative drivers that could shape the future competitive landscape.

At the heart of the report are **four original future scenarios**. Each scenario is carefully crafted and analysed, highlighting the opportunities and threats it presents. These scenarios offer **alternative visions of how Italian smart cities might evolve**, emphasizing the variability and uncertainty of the future while providing actionable insights for decision-makers and other stakeholders.

Lastly, strategic insights and surprising or overlooked patterns emerged during the study are included in the conclusive section, pointing out interesting suggestions and ideas that could be further developed.

This research is not just an exploration of potential futures—it is a guide for strategic thinking, innovation, and preparedness, **equipping Italian smart cities and innovation ecosystems to navigate the challenges and opportunities of the AI-societies** of tomorrow.

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Research Context

This white paper is part of the future-oriented research program conducted by the Observatory on Trends and Applications of Supercomputing, which aims to explore and anticipate the evolution of technology. The program encompasses a broad range of activities designed to map possible trajectories in High-Performance Computing, Artificial Intelligence, and Quantum Computing.

Prior to this study, the Observatory carried out extensive monitoring of market and funding trends, as well as detailed case study analyses, focusing on key thematic areas such as health, digital societies, manufacturing, climate, energy.

*The research presented in this paper represents the next step in the Observatory's program: a **more imaginative and conceptual approach to exploring the future**. By venturing into the field of Future Studies, this work develops original scenarios that envision multiple possible futures, providing both a strategic lens and a creative framework to understand the opportunities and challenges emerging from technological evolution.*

The Observatory on Trends and Applications of Supercomputing

The Observatory on Trends and Applications of Supercomputing is a project of the National Research Center in High-Performance Computing, Big Data, and Quantum Computing.

Realized by IFAB (International Foundation Big Data and Artificial Intelligence for Human Development), the Observatory was established with the ambitious goal of providing concrete and continuous support to businesses and public decision-makers, helping them navigate the challenges and opportunities of emerging technologies in the fields of HPC, Big Data, Quantum Computing, and Artificial Intelligence.

In particular, the Observatory:

- carries out continuous mapping of high-impact emerging technologies in the fields of supercomputing, Big Data, Quantum Computing, AI, and cloud, with a focus on their applicability in the industrial sector. More than 15 reports have already been published and collect more than 200 use cases of business applications implemented from enterprises of all sizes;
- provides recommendations for public decision-makers, promoting policies that facilitate the adoption of emerging technologies;
- supports Italian companies in their innovation and digital transition journey, guiding them towards strategic areas of investment and research;
- develops research studies in HPC Education to unveil the unmet needs and existing gaps between academic education and innovation challenges and to support the design of training programs.

Discover the reports and results produced by the Observatory on the website:
<https://osservatorio.supercomputing-icsc.it/report/>

Theoretical Foundations

Future is many, not one.
(Peter Bishop)

Futures Studies: the discipline that studies the futures

The discipline on which this research is grounded is called Futures Studies. It consists in **the study of postulating possible, probable and preferable futures**. It is intrinsically interdisciplinary: indeed, futures studies typically attempt to gain a holistic or systemic view because consider big and complex real systems that can be investigated only in a multidimensional perspective.

In terms of methodology, the futurists – this is one of the term for referring at those who study the future – employ a wide range of approaches, models and methods, many of which are derived from other academic or professional disciplines, from economics to political science, from computer sciences to statistics.

As the name itself of the discipline suggests, one of the fundamental assumptions in futures studies – adopted from the very beginning of this field of inquiry – is that **the future is not singular but plural** (Wells, 1932). Indeed, the future consists not of one inevitable future that is to be predicted, but rather of multiple alternative futures of varying likelihood which may be derived and described, and about which it is impossible to say with certainty which one will occur. In this sense, the epistemological determinist perspective is rejected by futurists together with the term prediction.

The object of study forces the discipline to follow some principles that have been enunciated in four points, known as Sardar's four laws of futures studies (Sardar, 2010).

“Futures studies are wicked”

Because of the complexity of the world, any exploration of the future has to face with such “wicked problems” (Churchman, 1967), difficult or impossible to solve because of incomplete, contradictory, and changing requirements that are often difficult to recognize. Moreover, because of complex interdependencies, the effort to solve one aspect of a wicked problem may reveal or create others. Futures studies are wicked

not only because of their object of study but because their very nature is wicked: indeed, the discipline is open ended, offering not single solutions but spaces of possibilities, and borrows ideas and tools from other different disciplines and sciences.

“Futures studies are MAD”

MAD is an acronym for Mutually Assured Diversity, a concept, first introduced by Sardar in 2004, according to that full preservation of our humanity requires that the diversity (of cultures, forms of living, ways of adjusting to change) is assured in any desired future. Futures studies need to take account of this diversity in their frameworks of concepts, theories and methods.

“Future studies are skeptical”

The skepticism of Futures studies has the aim of opening up pluralistic potentials. This is the only way walkable in a world in which uncertainty, complexity and accelerating change are so fundamental components of the future that the future cannot be known with certainty.

“Future studies are futureless”

This law is true not in the dictionary sense of “having no prospect of a future” but it holds in a more technical sense. Since we can have no definitively true knowledge of the future, the impact of all futures studies can only be evaluated in the present. This does not adhere to the falsification criteria à la Popper because, according to falsificationism, the value of a scenario or a future activity in general would be determined by their realization when the future will become present. At the opposite, the real relevance of the discourse lies in the present: all future activities, from forecasts to visioning, must have a direct impact on the present, orienting behavior, encouraging changes, managing anxiety.

The different kinds of futures

The primary effort in futures studies, then, is to identify and describe alternative futures, collecting quantitative and qualitative data about the possibility, probability, and desirability of change. In order to reach this identification of different futures, a variety of approach can be used.

At present, the most common model for futures studies includes four different types of futures, 'four Ps', or Possible, Plausible, Probable and Preferable futures, that can be represented in a visual way in the so-called futures cone.

Credits: [ISEEProject](#)

The class of **possible futures** includes all the kinds of futures we can possibly imagine – those which might happen, even if unlikely. They might, as a result, involve knowledge that we do not yet possess, or might also involve transgressions of currently accepted physical laws or principles. In the futures cone, possible futures correspond to the biggest range.

The **plausible futures** are futures that could happen according to our current knowledge of how things work. They stem from our current understanding of physical

laws, processes, causation, systems of human interaction, etc. This is clearly a smaller subset of futures than the possible and this is reflected from the futures cone too.

The class of **probable futures**, within the bigger class of plausible ones, contains those futures that are considered likely to happen and rely in part from the continuance of current trends. Some probable futures are considered more likely than others: the one considered most likely is often called *business-as-usual* and it consists in a linear extension of the present.

While the three classes of futures described above are all largely concerned with informational or cognitive knowledge, the fourth class, of preferable or **desirable futures**, is concerned with what we want to happen; in other words, these futures are largely emotional rather than cognitive. Because they derive from value judgements, they are more subjective than the previous three classes.

The approaches to study the futures: forecast, foresight, anticipation

After having described the main features of the different kinds of futures, we are going to examine the main approaches used for obtaining it, named Forecast, Foresight and Anticipation. These can be considered three different ways of thinking about the future.

The forecast approach consists in thinking at future looking at what has happened before, taking information about the past history of the system. Because of this feature, the forecast is a **past-oriented** approach and it is the closest approach to the determinist view of future.

Another approach is the foresight that, on the other side, takes directly on the future in an explorative viewpoint. This approach recognizes that the future is unpredictable and that there is not any certainty about it: then, a possible thing to do is imagine the future, staying

Credits: [Futures Platform](#)

bound by some data and information but providing qualitative models. In this sense, the foresight is considered a **future-grounded** approach. The main distinction between forecast and foresight is that the forecast considers only an extrapolation of the past toward the future, while **the foresight contemplates also surprises, novelties and changes.**

Credits: [Futures Platform](#)

The last type of approaches at futures studies is the anticipation. According to this approach, the future is far from being a problem of either extrapolation from trends or exploration of possible futures. **Through anticipation, the future becomes an issue of modifying and expand our capacity to act in the present** since the understanding of the future moves from a static belief of it as something that is 'there', to a dynamic view of the future as something that can be generated or consumed by our deeds (Poli, 2010). As a consequence, we have that anticipation is essentially a **present-oriented** approach because it includes the outcomes from forecast and foresight, using them for action.

The rise of strategic foresight

Over the years, futures studies has proven valuable across many fields, including policymaking, corporate strategy, education, and urban planning. By encouraging critical reflection on long-term impacts, it has helped organizations and societies prepare for uncertainty. Among its various sub-disciplines, strategic foresight stands out as one of the most important.

Strategic foresight adapts the methods of futures studies for direct use in organizational, business, and policy settings. It focuses on evaluating probabilities, assessing risks, and identifying concrete options that support decision-making. By emphasizing flexibility and adaptability, it enables decision-makers to align future strategies with specific goals and to manage uncertainty more effectively.

While futures studies often includes visionary or value-driven aims, strategic foresight prioritizes objectivity and actionable outcomes. It seeks to reduce subjective bias and assess options and probabilities in a pragmatic way. This approach ensures that insights can be interpreted and applied effectively across different contexts—whether in public policy, corporate strategy, or other domains.

Scanning the horizon: how strategic foresight starts

Developing strategic foresight projects usually requires starting from the recognition of on-going trends, phenomena, or signals, with the goal of make hypotheses on their evolution. The phase of Horizon Scanning should help answering the following questions:

What changes we should prepare for?
Which of the changes are relevant for us?
What kind of futures could we head to?

Many different types of “things” can be object of analysis at this stage. The following list details the most important ones.

Megatrends are the major long-term forces that are already shaping the present and that determine – or more precisely, constrain – possible futures. They are phenomena characterized by exponential dynamics, such as demographic growth, population aging, technological acceleration, digital transformation, labor automation, and climate change. Today, the analysis of megatrends forms the foundation of futures studies, as shown by the widespread use of this concept both in major consulting firms and in leading international institutions.

Interested in learning about megatrends? Explore the research of the [Italian Institute for the Future!](#)

Trends have a recognizable developmental path that can be, at least in theory, verified with quantitative data. A current trend is a push of a historical path-dependency, which we believe will continue into the future. Examples of trends include the growth of platform economy, plant-based meat substitutes, and the rising importance of cybersecurity.

Change drivers are either internal or external forces that shape the development of an organization, a market, a strategy, or a society. Some examples of change drivers are new legislation, new customer needs, technological change, and an emerging need for differentiation due to competition.

Weak signals are early information concerning potential discontinuities and emerging issues, such as new technologies which are still in their infant phase but which may see

a breakthrough at some point. They are not yet public knowledge, meaning that only a small group of people are aware of their potential.

Wild cards are speculations of low probability, high impact events. They are based on present issues that are boldly projected onto the future. By nature, they are sudden, rare, unexpected, surprising and disruptive discontinuities and shocks that can be either positive or negative. Some examples of wild cards that became true are the Chernobyl disaster, 9/11, the 2008 financial crisis and the Covid-19 pandemic.

Planning the scenarios: how strategic foresight ends (not)

Scenarios represent the main outcome of strategic foresight exercises. However, they are not an end in themselves: rather, they serve as a starting point for further reflection, planning, and decision-making. **Through scenarios, organizations can explore possible futures, test strategies against uncertainty, and identify both risks to avoid and opportunities to pursue.**

In scenario planning, at least four scenarios are usually developed by combining two key variables—or “critical uncertainties”—each expressed in opposite directions. For instance, if a company wishes to explore the impact of the war in Ukraine on its business, it could choose as critical uncertainties: (1) whether the conflict will persist or end in the long term, and (2) whether international sanctions will intensify or ease.

The four scenarios that emerge are “ideal types,” meaning they illustrate extreme situations rather than likely outcomes. Nevertheless, they are highly valuable: they help organizations clarify the futures they want to prevent and those they want to achieve, while also providing a foundation for strategies that mitigate risks and enable desired goals.

What is a scenario?

A scenario can be defined as a **description of a possible future situation, including paths of development which may lead to that future situation** (Kosow and Gaßner, 2008). It is not a comprehensive image of the future but its goal is to direct attention to clearly demarcated segments of reality.

Scenarios are hypothetical sequences of events constructed for the purpose of focusing attention on causal processes and decision points.

(Kahn & Wiener, 1967)

The selection and combination of key factors with regard to a future time horizon is also a construct because it forces to consider certain events as relevant and to ignore others: this perspective is similar to the modelling process used by science, since a selection of what is considered is always needed. Moreover, every scenario is based on (even if not always explicit) assumptions about how the future might one day look: **what direction certain trends might take, what developments might remain constant and which ones might change during the course of time.**

To fully understand what scenarios are, is also important to clarify what scenarios are not.

They are not predictions of the future...

...but help to explore what could happen and how to prepare for various contingencies.

They are not fixed plans...

...but frameworks that allow organizations or entire ecosystems to test the robustness of their strategies under different conditions.

They are not visions or aspirations...

...but constructs that present alternative possibilities, both desirable and undesirable.

They are not purely theoretical exercises...

...but practical instruments meant to inform choices, stimulate dialogue, and support collective learning.

Methodological approach

In our research, we decided to explore alternative futures for the usage of data in medium-small Italian municipalities that adopt smart solutions., fixing a time frame of 10 years from the start of the study (2035). The exploration of the issue was guided by the selection of specific strategic themes.

The Research Question

What possible scenarios by 2035 for the usage of data in medium-small Italian municipalities that adopt smart solutions?

Strategic issues of interest

Change in the HPC and Cloud infrastructure
Expected impact of EU investment on AI Factories and Giga Factories
Public-private & private-private partnerships
Skills development in the perspective of workforce transformation

This research was carried on in collaboration with Futures Platform, that provided the scenario methods most suitable for this topic and co-facilitated the activities of the study. The research involved different stages and was developed in three online workshops, hosting a [selected number of international experts](#).

Horizon Scanning

The first phase of the strategic foresight activity, was an horizon scanning. The goal was to identify the main trends perceived as future-shaping by the participants with respect to our research question.

The activity was supported by a tool of the Futures Platform website: the foresight radar.

The radar is divided into different sectors representing five crucial areas for the topic (political, social, environmental, technological, and economic) and the time frame increases moving away from the middle of the circle (2025) to the borders (2035).

Relevant phenomena were pre-selected by facilitators and positioned on the radar according to their belonging sector and time-frame. They also are depicted in different colours depending on their probability of occurrence or trend direction. Specifically:

- **Strengthening** - The presented issue is becoming more common or acute during the given timeframe. Most of its change potentially is still ahead.
- **Weakening** - The presented issue is becoming more unusual. During the given timeframe, most of its change potential or value has already occurred.
- **Weak Signal** - A small emerging issue in the present. At the given time frame, it is still hard to say whether it will become a trend or when it will hold impact in the future.
- **Established** - The presented issue had stabilised in its development. It has future relevance, but there is no indication that it will significantly strengthen or weaken within the given timeframe
- **Wild Card** - A possible but not probable event or change. Early information about a potential emerging risk or opportunity. The probability within the given timeframe is between 5% to 30%.

A detailed report of the radar's sectors and phenomena can be found in the [Annex](#).

After understanding this set up, the participants were asked to vote individually the phenomena according their perceived relevance to the topic.

The most voted phenomena were discussed and grouped in up to 5 umbrella categories that built the basis for the next step.

Driver Generation

Starting from the groups of phenomena obtained in the previous stage, denominated change drivers, the participants were asked to prioritize only two significant issues. These two were then used to generate the two key drivers – broad factors that determine future developments—that support the scenario narrative writing.

The two drivers chosen resulted in **data-driven approach & data security** and **Humans: reaction to smart cities**. They were depicted as horizontal and vertical axes on a 2x2 matrix. In order to complete the picture, for each driver, the participants were asked to name the two opposite ends of the axes.

Credits: [Futures Platform](#)

The process of driver generations resulted in the full visual representation of the 2x2 scenario matrix.

Scenario Narratives Writing

At the end of the meeting, the participants had described the four distinct scenarios, generated by the combination of two possible extremes of the axes.

To do so, the experts engaged in a guided discussion: the facilitators had pre-selected six thematic areas, corresponding to the strategic issues related to the research question, that lined the borders of the discourse. The six areas were:

- Change in the HPC/Cloud infrastructures;
- Expected impact of the EU investments on AI factories and Giga factories;
- Public-private and private-private partnerships;
- Skills development in the perspective of workforce transformation;
- Ethics and regulatory framework;
- National security.

The participants discussed how each of these areas would be affected in the specific scenario, thus defining each scenario peculiarities. The scenarios were also given an evocative title in order to move on to the last step of the study.

Scenario Analysis

After having described the four scenarios, the last stage was dedicated to scenario analysis.

Each scenario was carefully dissected in order to best identify its potential implications, focusing on both possible opportunities and threats. For each opportunity or threat, the experts were also asked to reflect on:

- possible actions to seize the opportunity or minimize the threat;
- responsible actors;
- implementation steps;
- timing;
- expected impact and measurement.

The four original scenarios crafted are then presented in the following paragraphs.

Scenario 1 – 1984

The scenario at a glance

By 2035, everything in Italian cities functions smoothly, thanks to the efficient and extensive use of data. However, privacy has completely disappeared, as all data is collected to ensure the system operates effectively. People's feelings about this are disregarded. Strict, highly specific rules dictate how everything works, leaving no room for interpretation. This shift hasn't been driven by politics, but by a cultural transformation shaped by the demands of technology.

Change in the HPC/cloud infrastructure

The infrastructure is highly developed; everything operates on the cloud to monitor and maintain system stability.

Expected impact of the EU investment on AI factories and giga factories

Many components are sourced from China, with limited consideration for security, human rights, or other concerns, as long as the system continues to function.

Public-private & private-private partnerships

Varies by city. In some cities, PPPs work well; in others, they don't – largely depending on the political orientation of the city's leadership. Right-leaning cities favour private actors, while left-leaning cities focus more on public actors.

Skills development in the perspective of workforce transformation

Experts in STEM and the humanities are trained, but the goal is to manipulate the population to ensure the proper functioning of the system, rather than to develop human-centric solutions.

Ethics and regulatory frameworks

Control and predetermination are the primary goals, with no regard for privacy or freedom. The system predicts likely outcomes; liberty is lost, but security is maintained.

National security

Technology from China poses risks. Cybersecurity remains a persistent issue, though quantum technology is expected to offer solutions.

Scenario Opportunities

Increased efficiency in public service delivery

To achieve this opportunity the central state should regain a stronger position, especially in services: major technological solutions should be state-owned and operated and initially the implementation would be difficult due to its massive scale, not to be expected before ten years from now. Some possible expected impacts would be fewer traffic accidents, fewer issues, and fewer disruptions in public services.

Economic benefits due to a central purchasing station

The central government should merge all purchasing platforms into a single platform across sectors and localities to favour mass purchases, pushing local authorities to carry out this implementation. The technology to do so is already existing, the government would need to create a legal framework, putting the time horizon to five years from now. The concrete benefits from this implementation would be the simplification of the purchase of standardized services and technology, coupled with a potential cost reduction.

Increased predictability in society brings stability and safer cities

The central government should push private operators—especially large companies—toward enabling interoperability and data exchange, therefore stronger

interoperability between devices leads to a greater predictability. In order to achieve so, a new operational framework should be introduced and promoted to guide this transition and the future impacts, tangible in three years from now, would consist improved security, greater safety, and financial savings.

Scenario Threats

Loss of perceived liberty among the people

Municipalities should inform people about why and how data sharing is taking place, allowing them to consider the potential risks associated with the loss of data ownership, they should also ensure data anonymisation immediately after collection. To do so they should provide guidelines on how to deal with the situation and organise meetings for the community to inform them, resulting in an immediate increased awareness among the population.

Scenario 2 – Shiny Happy People?

The scenario at a glance

In 2035, everything functions smoothly in Italian cities. Autonomous systems manage traffic and other operations. Privacy is fully protected; however, this has led to increased loneliness, as spontaneous encounters have become less frequent. Nevertheless, individuals may need to relax certain privacy protections to help tackle these pressing challenges. Data is shared among cities and other public actors to enable more effective actions.

Change in the HPC/cloud infrastructure

The infrastructure highly developed and highly interoperable.

Expected impact of the EU investment on AI factories and giga factories

European investments have played a very important role in helping the continent develop relevant industries. These investments have had a positive impact on the development of digital infrastructure and on security, with a positive effect on the labour market.

Public-private & private-private partnerships

In some cities, PPPs work well; in others, they do not - largely depending on the political orientation of the city's leadership. Right-leaning cities favour private actors, while left-leaning cities focus more on public ones.

Skills development in the perspective of workforce transformation

Many citizen science initiatives encourage cooperation among the population, not just among experts.

Ethics and regulatory frameworks

Cities are playing a growing role in regulatory matters. The central government provides general guidelines, and cities then translate these into more specific, local rules. There is an ongoing effort to strike the best balance between privacy and efficiency.

National security

Relying on European resources has led to increased safety and independence.

Scenario Threats

A normalised reality where people are 70% happy— there is no 100% happiness, no 0%— humanity and the human experiences are missing

Every actor should take the human factor into account in all stages, when setting up new research. This condition should be constantly considered, yet its expected impacts are very difficult to measure, with a high risk of misleading results.

Increased loneliness as life shifts to the virtual world

Systems are taking care of people's needs more frequently, even completing tasks such as optimisation of economics, pollution, and other factors, leading to a virtualisation of life. Central government and municipalities should identify and use the best aspects of both real and virtual worlds, avoiding to neglect the other. In particular, municipalities should organise events that promote socialization among people and foster cultural engagement, the impacts of these actions would be measured by the number of in-person meetings and monitoring activity on the internet.

Scenario 3 – The Middle Ages

The scenario at a glance

In 2035, Italian cities are malfunctioning. There is no efficiency in managing traffic or pollution. Municipalities lack the capacity to handle extreme weather events due to the absence of networks that would allow citizens to use data in their daily lives. There is no willingness to strive for improvement. Fear has become the most dominant emotion—fear of others, fear of disagreements due to a lack of control, and fear of technology and data collection. People have grown closer, but only within groups where others share the same views, leading to society fragmenting into clans.

Change in the HPC/cloud infrastructure

Development of the infrastructure has been stagnant, with very slow progress; the status quo largely persists.

Expected impact of the EU investment on AI factories and giga factories

There is little investment availability and a lack of coordination among nations. European investments have focused more on culture and education—aimed at reclaiming cultural values from technology.

Public-private & private-private partnerships

Use of PPPs have declined due to instability, leading to reduced willingness to collaborate. Entities prefer to act independently because of a lack of trust.

Skills development in the perspective of workforce transformation

The old-fashioned education system has been updated to include new skills for using technology and data, but progress remains small and stagnant.

Ethics and regulatory frameworks

There are strong, numerous laws, but they are inefficient due to poor communication and coordination between sectors. This results in a fragmented regulatory landscape, making it difficult for society to function effectively.

National security

Internal instability is growing, and crime is on the rise. Cybersecurity is relatively better, thanks to lower data usage; however, the state remains weak.

Scenario Opportunities

A simpler, less connected life that is not sustainable and will not last in time

The simpler life is an integral part of the scenario and cannot be affected.

People grow closer to one another and create an opportunity to reorient minds towards a different future

No actions could interfere with people taking a step back and imaging new futures.

Scenario 4 – Land of Hope

The scenario at a glance

In 2035, life in Italian cities have not changed much since 2025. There is a strong focus on the human side of living, but the use of data varies from city to city, with an overall gradual progress. However, there is still an ongoing struggle to find the best ways to implement technologies while maintaining a focus on human values.

Change in the HPC/cloud infrastructure

There is a lot of experimentation but no concrete, large-scale solutions yet. Efforts continue, with struggles to find the best possible way forward.

Expected impact of the EU investment on AI factories and giga factories

Some investments have been made, but there is a lack of focus. Investments are not large enough to keep pace with other countries; progress to the next level cannot be achieved with the current level of investment.

Public-private & private-private partnerships

These partnerships work in some situations but not in others; it depends on the people involved and the specific circumstances.

Skills development in the perspective of workforce transformation

There are experiments and bottom-up initiatives, but they are not sufficiently financed or supported to make a real impact.

Ethics and regulatory frameworks

Regulatory efforts exist, but in some cases, they are poorly targeted or misplaced. A lack of efficiency remains a significant problem in the regulatory landscape.

National security

There are no clear European rules dictating actions. The overall situation lacks clarity regarding the identification of risks.

Scenario Opportunities

Ongoing research on how technologies and data can improve life quality

As municipalities and local entities are closest to the people, they should take the lead and adopt a bottom-up approach in order to maintain a strong focus on encouraging communication between individuals, authorities, and companies at all levels to determine the best possible approach to organising the research. This process should start immediately and never be stopped: its results will provide researchers with a stronger and more solid foundation to better understand how to improve quality of life through technology and data.

Scenario Threats

Research results may be lost and not applied due to a lack of courage and initiative

People within every relevant entity should be engaged with this topic and strengthen coordination across all forums where these topics are discussed, creating opportunities to propose clear and actionable solutions for those involved in the discussions. However, the realization of a concrete plan depends on culture and courage and there is no straightforward solution. Schools, universities, and similar institutions should encourage this type of behaviour immediately, even though the expected effects can only be measured by observing real-life situations and people's behaviour.

Strategic Insights

Technology and data only are not enough

While the use of technology and data is emphasized in the scenarios **1984** and **Happy Shiny People?**, the scenarios **Middle Ages** and **Land of Hope** highlight that, without a focus on human experience, technology may paradoxically worsen it in certain ways.

The human experience should always be considered a key factor when exploring the future applications of smart technologies in Italian cities.

Security and efficiency at the expense of liberty and privacy

The use of smart solutions and data may deliver great benefits, but they can also erode individual privacy and liberty if not implemented properly as discussed in **1984** and **Happy Shiny People**. It remains unclear whether these issues can be fully addressed or mitigated.

PPPs are politicised or unreliable

Public-private partnerships (PPPs) and collaborations vary significantly across scenarios, with their success largely dependent on local political orientations and trust levels. This underscores the importance of building trust-based collaboration frameworks for future urban resilience.

Too much focus on the virtual world leading to loneliness and social problems

Focusing too heavily on digital solutions may, as in the scenario **Shiny Happy People**, encourage people to spend too much time in the online world. This can lead to increased loneliness, a problem already affecting many societies around the world. When researching and applying smart solutions in Italian cities, the social factor should be considered at every stage of the process.

Open Issues

Are social fragmentation and tribalism inevitable?

Communities risk becoming isolated, with people only trusting their own groups. This weakens city-wide cooperation, public services, and inclusive policies. Cities need deliberate strategies to rebuild shared spaces and cross-community trust.

Do people actually like the ongoing digitalization?

Growing appeal of simpler, slower lifestyles as a reaction to hyper-digitalisation: cities could harness this by promoting local culture, green spaces and low consumption initiatives. This shift could also open new economic models based on localism and wellbeing.

Can Italy improve its technology investment focus?

Many scenarios show scattered, uncoordinated tech investments. Without clear priorities, cities risk wasting resources and missing long-term value: clear, locally tailored tech roadmaps are essential for effective digital transitions.

Is municipal autonomy at risk?

The scenarios clearly showed how a strong dependence on external actors (foreign tech, EU funding, national policies) reduces local control: cities need to strengthen local capacities to avoid vulnerability to external shifts.

These questions deserve to be addressed and the scenarios discussed against them. Be part of this discussion and share your thoughts [here](#)!

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Annex – Phenomena and Trend cards

Political Sector

LATE 2020S

Most Western countries experience intensifying clashes related to socio-political bubbles, political hobbyism, and extremism that revolves around anti-immigration, nationalism and conservatism, social justice (“wokeism”), and, e.g., environmental activism. At the same time, democratic practices face intensifying pressure. In the 2024 democracy index, only 24 countries scored between 8.01 and 10 (out of 10) and were considered full democracies. 50 countries were ranked flawed democracies whose score lands between 6.01 and 8.00. 34 scored as hybrid regimes, while the number of authoritarian regimes was the largest at 59. Many of these were totalitarian countries with no civil rights or no possibilities to influence the country’s policies in any way. However, the most remarkable thing in the world democracy index is that it shows a long-term trend-like tendency where most countries are rather inclining towards more authoritarian practices than strengthening democratic practices.

EARLY 2030S

In the medium term, the struggle between democratic and authoritarian regimes intensifies. This is largely due to the frustrations of many people who have lived their whole lives in democracies but haven’t seen the system solving large societal problems nor guaranteeing economic prosperity. Second, many authoritarian countries have deliberately encouraged this sentiment in Western populations via different hybrid and information warfare operations. Third, by the early 2030s, the global economic, industrial, social, and political power balance is beginning to shift from the global West to the East. In many people’s minds, this development is likely to promote the authoritarian regimes’ benefits over the democratic ones.

LATE 2030S AND BEYOND

In the long run, there are probably fewer full democracies in traditional terms than there used to be, but at the same time the whole concept of democracy is in transition. First, AI avatars are steadily being introduced as a new tool allowing participatory municipal, regional or even national democracy. Later, prompted AI avatars are even introduced in some cases as tools of direct democracy, and finally we may even see cities or countries that are led by elected AI avatars. While authoritarianism remains the most common form of government, some new AI avatar practices will be introduced

in those as well. Eventually most countries end up being some sort of mixed models where AI plays a significant role in managing, and in some cases even ruling, the state.

Phenomena in the Political Sector

Cybersecurity Strengthening 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2025

The significance of cybersecurity increases continually at state, company and individual levels. Cybercriminals seek to advance both software and human-related vulnerabilities for, e.g., economic gains or stealing information. The annual losses caused by cybercrime are counted in billions.

National Security of Supply Strengthening 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2026

The world is becoming more unpredictable. This unpredictability increases the risk that nation-states will have to endure an increasing amount of different kinds of crises. All over the world, this may increase the nation-states' interest to ensure the security of supply on a national level. This means they will increasingly invest in domestic production, decrease dependency on international supply chains and start maintaining extensive emergency supply storage.

Etics of AI Strengthening 2023/25 - Timestamp: 2026

Advancements in artificial intelligence bring about new kinds of technology-related ethical questions that receive increasing attention in the future. The moral debate, legislation and practical guidelines regarding the development and utilisation of AI are becoming increasingly topical issues. The most urgent topic to be solved is about the moral guidelines of autonomous vehicles. Without solving it satisfactorily, the large fleets of otherwise ready robot taxis cannot enter the roads of world's numerous cities. The other hot topics awaiting to be solved as soon as possible are about the intellectual property rights of AI's creations, and the usage of AI in warfare.

Public-Private Partnership Strengthening 2024/28 - Timestamp: 2028

Public-private partnerships can be seen as an effective way to capitalise on the relative strengths of the public and private sectors to address problems that neither could tackle adequately on its own in respect of quality, access, financial optimisation, and innovation in different areas of the public sector. The success of these partnerships largely hinges on the terms and conditions of the contracts and transparency in decision-making.

Microchip Investments in the US&EU Strengthening 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2028

Semiconductor & microchip investments refer to capital, resources, and policy measures such as subsidies invested into the development, production, and innovation of semiconductor and microchip technologies. These investments represent a strategic means of securing economic stability, technological leadership, and national sovereignty in an era where the global economy is increasingly driven by digital innovation and connectivity. The US and the EU are aggressively trying to boost their domestic semiconductor and microchip industry due to heavy dependence on Chinese and Taiwanese production. These dependencies have raised security concerns, especially after the supply chain disruptions previously caused by the pandemic and, most recently, because of the increase in geopolitical tensions in East Asia.

AI in Participatory Democracy Strengthening: 2029/2120 - Timestamp: 2040

As technologies have increasingly become an essential feature of our daily lives, artificial intelligence may change the way we participate in democracy. Today, trust in democratic institutions is in decline, while many hope for novel means of decision-making and civic action. In the future, democracies may adopt AI systems and algorithmic avatars to a limited extent, enabling their users to automate civic participation and let avatars represent them in the democratic process.

Sovereign AI Strengthening: 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2028

Sovereign AI refers to a nation's aim to create and utilise artificial intelligence through its domestic resources. As generative AI's influence expands, governments will prioritise developing sovereign AI to maintain control over their data, economy, and security. This phenomenon will promote technological self-sufficiency among wealthy nations, but it may also worsen digital fragmentation and technological divide.

US as a Global Science Leader Strengthening:2025/2 -Timestamp: 2031

The long-standing dominance of the US in science and technology is eroding. The US government funding for major scientific agencies has been stagnating for years; in 2025 the public funding was decreased further along with new university research restrictions that were considered political limitations to the freedom of science by many. Meanwhile, China has ascended to the forefront as a scientific powerhouse by investing tremendous resources in research and development. The erosion of the US global competitive edge in science may limit future breakthroughs in critical technological sectors and medicine, with negative impacts on the economy, public health, and the ability to attract and train the next generation of scientists. This shift could lead to a brain drain away from the US and slowdown of its scientific progress, which again could undermine the US competitiveness and its global role.

China's aim with AI Strengthening: 2030/40 - Timestamp: 2032

The government of China aspires to make the country the leader in artificial intelligence development by 2030. As a one-party state, China can channel its national resources differently than its Western competitors, which may give it a head start. While it is yet to be seen whether China can sustain its predominant position in the AI development, China's AI supremacy would significantly boost its geopolitical, economic, and scientific standing in the world.

Collapse of International Cooperation Strengthening: 2030/2125 - Timestamp: 2032

Observable changes in world politics and global metrics suggest that overall international cooperation may be stagnating. While collaboration on key areas like climate, wellbeing, and innovation is still considered effective, geopolitical and security concerns are challenging and halting joint political, economic, and technological efforts. This is amplified by a transactional orientation towards foreign policy that has surged following the trade wars by the new US government. If this unilateral mentality grows stronger and geopolitical tensions deepen, it could lead to the collapse of international cooperation on several important fronts, such as peacekeeping and controlling climate change.

AI Leaders Strengthening: 2044/2124 - Timestamp: 2032

AI avatars may lead countries in the distant future. Algorithms promise to solve problems, ensure transparency, and enhance accountability, thus addressing complex leadership crises in contemporary governments. If designed without bias, AI presidents and state leaders could foster impartial and equitable governance. However, risks to freedom and privacy would remain significant.

Social Sector

LATE 2020S

The world's population will continue to grow for a few decades. Still, population growth is no longer based solely on an increasing birth rate but on people living longer than previous generations. In other words, the population is both growing in size and growing older. At the same time, humankind is also increasingly urbanising at an accelerating pace. While only 3% of people in the world lived in urban areas in 1800, the share has currently already reached approximately 55%. Every day, the number of urban residents increases by roughly 200,000. UN DESA estimates that the proportion of urban residents increases to 68% by 2050. In 1990 there were only ten megacities in the world with a population of more than 10 million people, whereas now, there are more than thirty megacities. Almost the entire generation of so-called 'baby boomers' born in Western countries after the wars will reach their retirement age at this point.

EARLY 2030S

As urbanisation accelerates, especially in Asia and Africa, megacities with more than 10 million residents will increase to around forty. Currently, population growth due to an increase in the birth rate mainly occurs in Sub-Saharan Africa. The youngest members of Generation Alpha are beginning their education, and Generation Z is entering the working life or their tertiary education. More and more representatives of the millennial 'Generation Y' are beginning to take on leading roles in business, politics, and market-defining companies. In emerging countries, absolute poverty and wars are declining, and the middle class is on the rise, but in the Western world, the middle class is shrinking, and the overall polarisation of society is accelerating.

LATE 2030S AND BEYOND

Life expectancy is increasing almost everywhere. However, the development has been most rapid in the West. Due to the increase in life expectancy, in particular, WHO estimates that population growth will continue until the year 2050 when the population is expected to be around 9.8 billion. As a result of accelerating urbanisation, a record 68% of humanity, or 6.5 billion people in total, are expected to live in cities. The continued growth in prosperity and population is overshadowed by the possibility of a major international war and the collapse of states, the increase in displacement due to climate change and migration, diseases of affluence and modern lifestyles, risk of pandemics and AI changing the working life too quickly, and the blatant inequality of

the population, which can lead to unrest and terrorism, or at least weaker health and shorter life expectancy among the impoverished population.

Phenomena in the Social Sector

Restricting use of Tech Strengthening: 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2026

Governments, education institutes, and workplaces around the world are increasingly cracking down on the use of certain technologies within their countries and institutions. Concerns about the negative impacts and dangers of technology are driving these changes, from smartphone bans in classrooms to AI tool restrictions in universities and corporate settings. If this trend intensifies, it may put tech companies under growing pressure and could introduce considerable changes to youth culture, improve mental health, or potentially hamper students' professional development.

AI Driven Mass Misinformation Strengthening: 2027/30 - Timestamp: 2026

The digital content available online is increasingly produced or at least edited by artificial intelligence systems rather than being authentic or made by human creators. As AI-generated content is becoming cheaper, better in quality, and easier for anyone to produce, it becomes more prevalent, and discerning between authentic human-created content and AI-generated content is becoming increasingly challenging. We may end up quite soon in a situation where highly sophisticated AI-generated content not only fills the internet, but especially disinformation is disseminated on a mass scale, potentially turning the internet into an untrustworthy landscape.

Right to Privacy Weakening: 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2027

People carry along an increasing number of mobile devices that are constantly connected to internet services as well as other devices in their vicinity. This enables continuous surveillance and monitoring as well as accurate profiling. Piece by piece, this development eats away our right to privacy. In the future, exchanging privacy for convenience may become the norm. Yet, the eroding trust towards tech-giants may also lead people to demand more control over their data.

Urbanization

Strengthening: 2023/25 - Timestamp: 2027

Urbanisation, which began during the industrial revolution, has continued to the present day. Already now, half of the world's population lives in urban areas, and the portion is expected to grow further. Cities can bring about vast opportunities and benefits through economies of scale and network effects. On the other hand, rapid urbanisation also imposes numerous challenges.

Marginalisation of Minorities and Disadvantaged Groups

Strengthening: 2025/30 - Timestamp: 2028

Marginalised minorities and disadvantaged groups in Europe, including Roma, migrants, people with disabilities, and racial or ethnic minorities, continue to face systemic exclusion through discriminatory policies, inadequate social services, and underrepresentation in decision-making. Despite EU initiatives like the Anti-Racism Action Plan, recent reports show that over €1 billion in public funding has even fueled segregation and rights violations, underscoring persistent structural barriers to equality

Rise of Anti-Tourism

Strengthening: 2024/27 - Timestamp: 2028

Overtourism is causing a growing anti-tourist sentiment among locals in some cities and other popular destinations. Online hypes create high tourist influxes in specific destinations, leading to overcrowding, rising living costs, environmental damage, and the disappearance of local culture and vital resources. As locals express their discontent via public protests, some places have begun to introduce tourist-limiting regulations. These regulations and the need to prioritise sustainable practices to ensure tourism benefits both visitors and residents could drive vacation costs up in the future and divert tourists to new destinations.

Right to Privacy

Weakening: 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2027

People carry along an increasing number of mobile devices that are constantly connected to internet services as well as other devices in their vicinity. This enables continuous surveillance and monitoring as well as accurate profiling. Piece by piece, this development eats away our right to privacy. In the future, exchanging privacy for convenience may become the norm. Yet, the eroding trust towards tech-giants may also lead people to demand more control over their data.

Technostress

Strengthening 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2029

Stress induced by overexposure to technology, also known as technostress, now extends beyond the workplace. The digitalisation of work, rapid technological advancements, and constant connectivity are some of the factors that drive this phenomenon, which can lead to cognitive overload and emotional exhaustion. For employees, unmanaged technostress can result in burnout and lack of professional growth. Meanwhile, organisational leaders may need to ensure that workplace wellness initiatives promote healthy technology use.

Anti-Intellectualism

Strengthening 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2029

In the past decade, anti-intellectual rhetoric has been used repeatedly and successfully by populists in key elections and referendums in Western nations (including the US presidential elections of 2016 and 2024 and the Brexit referendum), gaining significant support from people with anti-intellectual attitudes. Data suggests that trust in scientists in the US decreased 16% between 2019 and 2023. Growing anti-intellectualist attitudes within a society will stifle freedom of speech, inhibit innovation, and lead to the defunding of research institutes. It can also lead to bad policy decisions with significant long-term implications for the health and prosperity of people.

Losing the Sense of truth

Strengthening 2030/40 - Timestamp: 2029

Our ability to distinguish truth from fiction is increasingly eroding in a truthless world shaped by modern information technologies, a business model based on knowledge extraction and personalisation, and state-driven campaigns. As disinformation, misinformation, fake news, deepfakes, actual information warfare, etc. grow increasingly prevalent, people cannot trust the information they read, hear, and watch. This could lead to a situation of all-encompassing epistemic babble, where a fully collapsed information ecosystem would make it impossible for our societies to collectively respond to a crisis, such as a war or a pandemic, or a complex challenge like climate change.

Trust in Public Authorities

Weakening 2024/27 - Timestamp: 2029

Trust in public authorities and leaders is declining around the world. For example, according to a 2023 Gallup analysis, public trust in the US government, judiciary, media, military and other key institutions has declined. Overall, the country has been experiencing a very low trust environment since the 1970s. Poor institutional performance, slow response to global crises, rampant disinformation, increasing economic inequality and other drivers are depriving citizens of faith in their public institutions. The continued erosion of trust may trigger a vicious cycle of internal conflicts and even deeper distrust.

AI teacher

Weakening 2028/2125 - Timestamp: 2029

In the future, artificial intelligence (AI) may largely replace teachers. Much of the routine work of teachers can already be automated, but in addition, AI could also help students learn faster and more efficiently than under the guidance of a human teacher alone. In this scenario, the role of the teacher would be more akin to that of a mentor, while AI takes care of the actual learning process. In the future, the use of AI teachers could allow faster degree completion, reduce socio-economic disparities, and better address individual learning differences.

Revival of Luddite Movements

Strengthening 2035/2124 - Timestamp: 2032

Public scepticism towards AI and automation could fuel a resurgence of neo-Luddism, an anti-technology movement. Neo-Luddites, echoing their 19th-century predecessors, challenge unchecked technological progress, aiming to protect human labour and societal values. Fears of job displacement and ethical concerns are key drivers of the protests and political activism associated with these movements. If their influence grows, these movements could lead to legislative restrictions on AI and automation technologies, potentially slowing AI adoption and advancements.

Birth rates

Weakening: 2024/35 - Timestamp: 2032

Birth rates have been declining globally for decades. The decline has been the steepest in the developed and industrialized countries. A low fertility rate is likely to lead to economic and, subsequently, also social changes.

Artificial+Robot Coworkers Strengthening: 2025/29 - Timestamp: 2032

The use of automation and AI-enabled robots has been on the rise in the workplace. A wide range of businesses will continue to increase their investments in AI and automation in order to maximise productivity and seek greater financial benefits. Automation is likely to transform existing jobs by removing routine tasks, speeding up and adding quality to some tasks, and creating more space for creativity and insight in jobs assisted by AI software.

Autocracies vs. Democracies Strengthening: 2025/29 - Timestamp: 2033

While autocracies are currently the majority in the world, liberal democracy has been on the decline for almost two decades now. With geopolitical, economic and technological competition becoming ever fiercer, there is an intensifying struggle in the international arena for global hegemony between democracies and autocracies. Concerns are growing that the world may find itself in a new Cold War between autocracies, led by China and supported by Russia, on one side, and democracies, looking with concern at the political development of the United States, on the other. Other countries may increasingly have to decide to which camp their allegiance belongs to.

Adapting to Democratic Shrinkage Strengthening: 2033/45 - Timestamp: 2033

Approaches to adapt to demographic shrinkage may offer a sustainable alternative to traditional growth models that pursue constant economic growth. As global birth rates fall and societal ageing accelerates, societies may be required to strategically adapt to demographic realities rather than resisting or reversing inevitable demographic decline. This adaptation involves proactively aligning policies, resources, and services to better serve shrinking populations and putting an emphasis on valuing quality of life over profits. The shift may ultimately produce communities better equipped for long-term sustainability.

Technological Sector

LATE 2020S

Science, by nature, is self-correcting, which means that discoveries change and supplement previous interpretations continuously. Science is also cumulative, indicating that all previously confirmed findings give a basis for new ones. A novel technology, like AI, or a remarkable scientific breakthrough in some field, may provide an explanation, or even a shortcut to a whole new level, for some other area of study. Additionally, the processing power of computers and the number of researchers are unmatched in human history. For these reasons, science will likely keep up its accelerating rate in the future, unless some unexpected development or societal change reduces the resources available for research dramatically across the world.

EARLY 2030S

There will be an enormous demand for new highly skilled specialists, particularly data scientists, coders, cybersecurity professionals, and AI researchers and developers, in the short and medium term. In the medium term, demand for know-how and expertise in so-called STEM fields (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) will likely grow considerably. A central reason for this is that virtually all production fields will become smarter, more networked and more complicated, which means that productivity cannot rise further without the latest knowledge in STEM fields. However, advances in the development and application of various artificial intelligence systems could boost productivity significantly, replace some high-skills occupations and in this way moderate the growth of demand for STEM-educated professionals.

LATE 2030S AND BEYOND

In the longer term, several large-scale scientific breakthroughs are to be anticipated, which will revolutionise their respective disciplines. Examples of this include, among others, industrial revolution 5.0, quantum computing and technology, the next generation of AI, gene- and biomedicine 2.0, a fully functional brain-computer link, nanotechnology, renewable energy and circular economy revolutions, a graphene revolution, DNA-data storing, space economy, and electrification and automatization of transportation, as well as using hydrogen as a fuel in vehicles. Also, in the conventional hard sciences like physics, radical findings are likely to take place, which, once realised, have the potential to transform the world and human possibilities in a fundamental way. Such revolutionary developments could be, for instance, the discovery of dark energy and matter, detection of the fourth dimension, multiverse, or fifth fundamental

interaction of nature, quantum teleportation of physical objects becoming feasible, artificial generation of atoms and matter, e.g. from basic particles or energy, an artificial wormhole, warp drive, or antigravitation.

Phenomena in the Technological Sector

Smart Grids

Strengthening: 2024/28 - Timestamp: 2025

Large markets, such as the EU, USA, China, and India, are moving from vulnerable and inefficient old energy grids towards new grid solutions. In a decentralised smart grid powered by AI, regional control centres coordinate a two-directional flow of useful information and the delivery of electricity between producers and consumers. This could open up the potential to generate a value of hundreds of billions of dollars to society and promote the efficient and sustainable use of electricity.

Cloud Computing

Strengthening: 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2025

Massive computing power and storage capacity can be accessed cost-effectively and in real-time through the use of cloud computing. The market and use of cloud computing services are anticipated to grow thanks to the business opportunities it creates. Cloud computing will play an essential role in the emergence of smart cities, future of work, autonomous vehicles, as well as in bringing the use of big data and the Internet of Things to the industrial settings. Cloud computing may also give rise to oligopolistic tech giant dominance or it might become a part of the intensifying geopolitical competition.

Nanotechnologies and Materials

Strengthening 2023/28 - Timestamp: 2029

Nanotechnologies and materials provide significant improvements to objects, equipment, and processes in everyday use. Advancements on the nano-level improve efficiency and accuracy in many fields of industry and science.

Smart Countryside

Strengthening: 2025/2120 - Timestamp: 2027

The development of smart technologies and networks will create new opportunities to bring life to rural communities. If the technologies can improve livelihood conditions, access to services and the efficiency of logistics, the countryside may become vitalized in a completely new way instead of continuing to die out. However, this is unlikely to happen without a bold strategy and a long-term investment to support it.

AI in Healthcare

Strengthening: 2024/28 - Timestamp: 2026

AI and machine learning will play an increasingly important role in medical decision-making, diagnostics, treatment plans, and cure development. AI is likely to lighten the load of individual doctors and bring a long-needed efficiency boost. Furthermore, treatment results and patient survival will improve, and costs will decrease, as diseases can be identified early on and treated with precision. Also, medical care can be made more accessible as AI-powered chatbots can provide medical advice for those who otherwise cannot easily visit a doctor's office.

Smart Wearables

Strengthening: 2029/33 - Timestamp: 2028

Smart wearables, or wearable tech, refers to all kinds of smart materials, devices, sensors, and analysis equipment that people can wear. Various bracelets offering biomonitors sports training or augmented phone functions have dominated the market. Still, wearables with more functionality, such as smart wearables and smart clothing, will gain more popularity in the coming years.

Edge Computing

Strengthening: 2027/32 - Timestamp: 2028

Edge computing refers to the processing and storing data near its point of origin. The data is not transferred to an external data centre but a server located, for example, next to a base station, will take care of the handling and warehousing. This reduces latency, improves data security and possibly also lowers costs.

Optical Computing

Strengthening: 2028/45 - Timestamp: 2029

Optical computers could play an important role in addressing the growing demand for computational power and energy efficiency. The concerns with fast-increasing digital emissions and energy consumption and the advancements in artificial intelligence have accelerated the development of optical computing technologies. Currently, optical computing is applied primarily in niche areas. In the future, this technology could offer AI companies significant benefits, including lower energy consumption, while also enabling breakthroughs in fields such as materials science, where more advanced computation models are needed.

Smart Cities

Strengthening: 2029/40 - Timestamp: 2029

With rapid urbanisation and challenges imposed by the growing urban population, cities around the world have started to reinvent themselves through smart city initiatives. Smart cities have become an icon of a new digitally facilitated form of living in urban space, offering a more sustainable and livable environment. Our assessment indicates that smart cities will steadily grow in the future; however, they may present either a utopia or a dystopia, depending on their development and governance.

DNA Data Storage

Strengthening: 2028/40 - Timestamp: 2033

DNA data storage is the process of encoding and decoding digital data to DNA strands. It holds significant potential as DNA is very compact and durable. Storing data in DNA also presents a sustainable option to data centres that consume a lot of energy. Currently, the process is very slow and expensive, therefore not suitable for scaling up to commercial use. It may, however, soon be possible to use DNA for storing cold data that doesn't need to be accessed often.

Graphene Revolution

Strengthening: 2029/39 - Timestamp: 2033

Due to its many desired qualities, graphene is superior to other currently known materials. It is very light, durable, and translucent, and it also conducts heat and electricity well. Research and development work on graphene is buzzing because it is believed that graphene can provide revolutionary improvements to the performance of current materials, components, and machines and form a groundwork for many entirely innovations.

Quantum Computers

Strengthening: 2030/45 - Timestamp: 2033

Quantum computing could one day radically reshape the world. It could allow solving challenges that the best supercomputer cannot even handle and possibly break current encryption schemes. While quantum computing is still in its infancy, it is crucial for organisations to start preparing for the quantum era. When the technology matures, businesses will shift to quantum-resistant cryptography, and the high computing power will accelerate the development of artificial intelligence.

Energy Prosumerism Strengthening: 2030/40 - Timestamp: 2033

Energy prosumers are electricity consumers that produce part of their electricity needs and inject excess production onto the distribution network. New connected technologies and the fall in the cost of solar and wind technologies are transforming energy systems in the direction of decentralised, renewable, and demand-responsive smart configurations. Prosumers are mainly motivated by environmental concerns, technological interests, and self-consumption rather than economic returns. However, a range of prosumer business models is emerging and increasing the energy security while decreasing capacity demand on power grids. If regulation and government infrastructure investments follow in suit, prosumers will become a positive disruptive force in the electricity industry.

Economic Sector

LATE 2020S

The International Monetary Fund (IMF) forecasts in their 2024 Outlook steady but slow growth for the world economy in the coming years. Their baseline forecast projects 3.2 per cent growth for 2025, which is the same where the growth has been since 2023 (World Bank predicts 2.6-2.7% for the same period). According to the IMF, there is a slight acceleration for advanced economies, where growth is expected to rise from 1.6 per cent in 2023 to 1.7 in 2024 and 1.8 in 2025. The projected growth will be offset by a modest slowdown in emerging markets and developing economies from 4.3 per cent in 2023 to 4.2 per cent in both 2024 and 2025. The World Bank's estimation mostly aligns with these figures, but it also emphasises that the situation in the world's poorest economies is becoming more worrisome. For inflation, IMF forecasts a steady decline, from 6.8 per cent in 2023 to 5.9 in 2024 and 4.5 in 2025, with advanced economies returning to their inflation targets sooner than developing markets and economies. Core inflation is generally projected to decline more gradually. At the same time, IMF sees dimmer prospects for growth in China and other large emerging market economies, which is putting weight on trading partners. They also identify globally persistent structural frictions that prevent capital and labour from moving to productive firms, which is leading towards lower growth in output per person than predicted earlier.

EARLY 2030S

The IMF forecasts just 3.1% global growth for the turn of 2030, which would be the lowest in decades but still nearly the same as what is projected for the late 2020s in general. In the medium term, China may become the world's largest economy. Its big tech companies (BATHX) will increase their international influence significantly and begin to seize world markets in the same way as big US technology companies did earlier. China is advancing and spreading its military and economic influence throughout the world, especially in Africa and Asia. China is taking the lead at least in the global control of the world's primary raw materials and infrastructure investments, and possibly also in greentech, AI, and IoT development, and their commercialisation. Yet, China's smart technology dominance is likely hindered by a lack of semiconductor and advanced chips production, in which the US and the EU together with Taiwan are progressing faster.

LATE 2030S AND BEYOND

In the long term, the direction of the global economy will be largely determined by the development pace, scope, regulations, and adoption of quantum computing and AI and their influence on the economy, industries, and workforce skills needs. China aims to become the global leader especially in AI, which would strengthen its effort to dominate the global economy. Yet, the Chinese population is ageing, meaning that the country might lose its dynamic edge especially to the US, which still has a young and vibrant population and most likely also a good capability to attract foreign talent. However, there are also many uncertainties that may affect the direction quite significantly. The world economy may descend to stagnation. Extensive protectionism and economic blocs led by China and the US might emerge. This includes the establishment of both the Asian Union and the Transatlantic Trade Union, and yuan becoming an equal global currency with the dollar. China may invade Taiwan, which could lead to doomsday outcomes. India may begin to challenge China. China may internally collapse. And globalisation may start flourishing again, meaning that talent migration could change to West-to-Asia migration.

Phenomena in the Economic Sector

Demand for Basic Digital Skills Strengthening: 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2026

Europe faces a significant gap in basic digital skills among its population and emerging workforce: only about 55–56% of Europeans currently meet the EU's definition of "basic digital competence," falling short of the 80% target set for 2030. This deficit will hinder youth entering the job market and complicate broader economic digitalisation unless robust education, training, and upskilling initiatives - like the Digital Skills and Jobs Platform and €1.3 b investment under the Digital Europe Programme - are rapidly scaled up.

Competitiveness of the EU Weakening: 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2027

A fragmentation of EU-level strategic investments, the modest amount of total available investment capital, ageing populations, slower innovation and lack of dynamism, energy crises, a weak role in geopolitics, and regulatory complexity are regressing EU's competitiveness globally. These issues are compounding the industrial decline, weakening Europe's ability to innovate and compete against dynamic economies in Asia and North America. Without substantial reforms, the EU risks fragmentation and further marginalisation in the global economic hierarchy.

Data Center Expansion Strengthening: 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2027

As the world is shifting towards a cloud-driven digital economy, demand for expanding data centre capacity is growing rapidly. The more sophisticated data analytics become through big data and the adoption of AI and IoT, the more investment will be made in servers and storage space. Data centres will take up increasingly more physical space and require ultra-low-latency connectivity. Therefore, the data centre market will continue to expand along with hyperscale and edge computing solutions. Existing sustainability concerns related to energy, water and land demand may drive the emergence of new business models, such as data centres at sea.

AI Bubble Burst Wild Card 2025/40 - Timestamp: 2032

The exponential growth in the value of AI-related stocks has led to speculations that the industry may be following the familiar path of an economic bubble. The recent AI boom has increased the market value of big tech businesses and chipmakers significantly over a short period of time, raising concerns that the markets may be heading towards a sudden freefall at some point.

Rare-Earth Elements Weakening: 2024/28 - Timestamp: 2029

Europe has witnessed unprecedented high energy prices recently, and there might be no return to low prices in the foreseeable future. Several factors have contributed to the situation. High taxation to phase out fossil fuels, closing down nuclear power plants, electrification of traffic, and challenges in ensuring grid stability while modernising production all have their role in the energy puzzle. The newest driver that is pushing the European energy markets into unprecedented change is the war in Ukraine and its impacts on the continent's need to rely less on Russian energy supply and be more self-sufficient.

Global Workforce Competition Strengthening: 2025/29 - Timestamp: 2029

Many countries suffer from shrinking total and working-age populations, which might increase competition on the global labour market. Labour scarcity is a common phenomenon in socially and economically developed countries that suffer from low fertility and an ageing population. This puts upward pressure on wages and reduces the economic competitiveness of the country. A variety of powerful economic factors are combining to change the way work is done, but labour is most likely to remain in high demand. How to attract migrants with the right skill set might become a top priority for countries that are increasingly competing for workers on the global labour market.

Greentech Bubble Burst

Wild Card 2027/32– Timestamp: 2032

The field of greentech is expanding rapidly due to the global transition to renewable energy sources. However, the overheated greentech boom around electric vehicles, solar panels, and wind turbines is also becoming a growing concern. With the rise of alternative green fuels and other issues surrounding electric grids, e-waste, and the insufficient production of needed raw materials, the current boom of the leading green technologies may end.

Data Center Bubble Burst

Wild Card 2027/33 - Timestamp: 2032

A new approach to building advanced AI models without data centres could disrupt the new data centre construction boom and cast doubt on the viability of many ongoing data centre projects. Currently, the data centre boom is driven by the rapidly growing social media video streaming and widespread adoption of AI tools and the fear of falling behind in the AI race. Therefore, almost all large tech companies have rushed to build large-scale data centres across the world to support AI development.

Supply Chain Transparency

Strengthening: 2027/32– Timestamp: 2032

Reoccurring human rights violations and eco-scandals along the supply chains of major companies have heightened the demand for transparency in production conditions and environmental impacts of products, having led to new supply chain regulations. Frameworks like the EU's Digital Product Passport (DPP) promote informed purchasing, legal compliance and circular practices. In the future, blockchain-based innovations may support businesses in making complex supply chains transparent, combating fraud, and protecting sensitive data. The growing demand for supply chain transparency could extend product lifetimes, boost consumer trust, enhance company resilience, and encourage circular business models.

Changin European Energy Market

Strengthening:2025/28–Timestamp: 2028

Europe has witnessed unprecedented high energy prices recently, and there might be no return to low prices in the foreseeable future. Several factors have contributed to the situation. High taxation to phase out fossil fuels, closing down nuclear power plants, electrification of traffic, and challenges in ensuring grid stability while modernising production all have their role in the energy puzzle. The newest driver that is pushing the European energy markets into unprecedented change is the war in Ukraine and its impacts on the continent's need to rely less on Russian energy supply and be more self-sufficient.

Everything becomes cheap due to AI

Strengthening: 2040/2125– Timestamp: 2033

In one of the most optimistic scenarios from a certain perspective, the super-fast and profound GenAI development may lead to a society where almost all services, food, and products are nearly free. In such smartly automatised societies people wouldn't have to work anymore to ensure their livelihoods. There would be a universal basic income in effect that would be sufficient to have a quite comfortable lifestyle. In this case, the emerging key challenge would be to reshape the role of people, to refine what it is to be human, and to find a new way to build a purposeful life.

Environmental Sector

LATE 2020S

The recycling of raw materials and waste, adhering to the principles of sustainable development, and various kinds of environmental thinking will continue to increase. Numerous NGOs and political parties will pressure governments to commit themselves and foster international climate agreements, restrictions on the use of dangerous chemicals, and bans on items such as plastic bags. At the same time, nature and natural resources will be seen as enablers of economic and social growth and development, which will decrease the area of unspoiled nature year by year. Initiatives towards circular economy, efficient use of resources, and zero emissions will feature visibly in the communication of public and private organisations, but the actual efficiency of these may still leave a lot to be desired during the rest of the 2020s.

EARLY 2030S

Governments will also boost the demand for circular economy and cleantech in the medium term by increasing environmental regulation and financial incentives. New groundbreaking cleantech solutions, such as construction material out of waste and self-healing buildings, CO₂ capture and repurposing e.g. to fuel or food, LED lighting in food production, and turning landfills into mines for raw materials, will progress rapidly, expanding the markets in the sector. It is expected that cleantech markets will continue their long-term annual growth of more than 10 per cent and will increasingly shift from Europe to developing countries. Sustainability considerations could also increasingly drive production closer to markets through the deployment of new production technologies, partly eliminating the need for long, environmentally negative shipping lanes.

LATE 2030S AND BEYOND

The use of new sustainable technologies will bring demonstrably significant resource and cost savings to governments, organisations and individuals. In the late 2030s, adhering to the principles of sustainable development, recycling raw materials and waste, and utilising innovations such as an intelligent electricity network and turning carbon dioxide back into fuel will begin to be commonplace. These will not be regarded as special environmental efforts but as reasonable and economically sound ways of operating. For example, the utilisation of biology in the growing of packaging material and the production of low-CO₂ protein is becoming commonplace by necessity rather than ideological reasons.

Phenomena in the Environmental Sector

Data Consumption & Digital Emissions

Strengthening: 2024/27 - Timestamp: 2025

Increasing data consumption is a fast-growing global megatrend. The key reasons for this development are general digitalisation and especially the increasing usage of smartphones, on-demand streaming services, the vast popularity of video-based material on social media platforms, search engine usage, and cryptocurrency mining. Yet, data consumption is even expected to skyrocket from the current levels in the near future. All this is leading to even larger need of data centres, submarine data cables, satellites, base stations, and available energy that again mean higher digital emissions.

Climate Change

Strengthening: 2040/2123 - Timestamp: 2026

Based on the evidence from all indicators, the Earth's climate is changing and warming at an exceptional rate. Since 1880, the highest average temperatures on our planet have been measured in the last 20 years, and many temperature records have been set in the most recent years. Long-term effects of climate change will include increases in extreme weather events including large storms, heat waves, polar vortex fluctuations, droughts, and heavy rainfalls; thawing of permafrost, ice sheets, and glaciers; and sea level rise. In the most extreme worst-case scenario, the global average temperature could even rise by 4.4°C, which would put the global food production in real jeopardy, devastate living conditions in vast regions that are now densely populated, and could even lead to the collapse of entire ecosystems around the world.

Climate Anxiety & Panic

Strengthening: 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2027

Climate anxiety has spread throughout developed countries in the last few years. It is not currently recognised as an official medical condition as it is partly seen as an understandable reaction to the threat an endangered ecosystem poses to humans. On an individual level, however, if a person does not find a constructive way to cope with their anxiety, it may start severely impacting their ability to function. An increasing number of especially young people have started needing medical treatments such as tranquillisers or mental hospitalisation due to experiences of climate anxiety.

Environmental & Pigouvian Taxes Strengthening:2025/29–Timestamp: 2029

Climate change, limited natural resources, and pollution are forcing societies to find ways to steer production and consumption in a sustainable direction. Environmental and Pigouvian taxes, e.g., such as a flight tax and a carbon tax, are important tools to discourage actions that damage the environment. However, these taxes suffer from being inefficient and their effect is difficult to measure. While Pigouvian taxes will be applied only to a limited number of economic sectors for the time being, increasing number of countries could implement some form of Pigouvian tax in order to steer more innovation and investments towards green technologies.

Restraining Emissions Strengthening: 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2027

Restraining emissions is crucial to mitigate global warming. To achieve reductions in greenhouse gas production, both political and technological solutions are needed. The changes will particularly affect the energy sector and transportation. Besides emission reductions, policies addressing the warming climate may result in new jobs and increased innovation. However, it is unclear whether the transition to a climate-neutral society is doable in the planned time frame, and how this affects the economic wellbeing of citizens in general.

Extreme Weather Events Strengthening: 2025/28 - Timestamp: 2025

Extreme weather events are becoming more frequent and intense around the world, largely due to human-induced climate change. These events include extreme wildfires, droughts, heatwaves, floods and heavy rainfall, tropical cyclones, as well as sand and dust storms. The effects of these events are already felt, but they will intensify under the current projections. Impacts will be felt by people, the planet, and the global economy as these events come to threaten our health, global food systems, global trade and transport systems, and cause severe ecological destruction to a higher extent than today in the decades to come.

Climate Refugees + Migration Wild Card:2029/39 -Timestamp: 2031

Many currently inhabited areas may become unliveable in the future due to climate change. This would lead to massive waves of climate refugees, forcing countries to rethink their immigration and refugee policies. The current estimates of potential climate refugees range from 25 million to 1.5 billion by 2050.

Cleantech

Strengthening: 2027/32 - Timestamp: 2028

Clean and green tech refers to technologies, products, and services with minimal negative environmental impact and contribute to sustainable development. It encompasses a broad range of innovative solutions that address environmental challenges, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, conserve resources, and promote a transition to a more sustainable and low-carbon economy while maintaining performance and productivity. Cleantech's ongoing development and adoption are expected to have a transformative impact on society.

Biomimetic Composites

Weak Signal - Timestamp: 2031

Biomimetic composites are materials engineered to mimic natural structures or processes found in living organisms. These composites often combine synthetic or natural materials with biological components or principles to achieve specific properties or functionalities. By drawing inspiration from nature, biomimetic composites aim to replicate features such as strength, flexibility, self-healing, or environmental adaptability, offering innovative solutions in fields ranging from materials science and engineering to medicine.

Carbon Dioxide Removal Strengthening: 2030/40 - Timestamp: 2031

Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) refers to methods which involve removing CO₂ from the atmosphere through nature-based and technological solutions. Examples include tree planting, forest conservation, soil carbon sequestration, direct air capture, and enhanced rock weathering. While reducing greenhouse gas emissions remains crucial, CDR complements emissions reduction efforts by removing the excess carbon dioxide that has accumulated over time. By restoring the balance of the carbon cycle, CDR can help limit global warming, mitigate the impacts of climate change, and enhance the resilience of ecosystems.

Nuclear & Radiological Accidents Wild Card 2025/50 - Timestamp: 2032

Nuclear and radiological accidents pose unpredictable global risks despite their low likelihood. Historical incidents like the Chernobyl disaster highlight their catastrophic potential. Conflicts, climate change, and increased nuclear energy development are some of the factors heightening the risks of nuclear and radiological accidents. Should such an accident occur, it could trigger broader disagreements, environmental damages, and socio-economic instabilities.

Nature Positive Strengthening 2028/33 - Timestamp: 2028

As humanity faces the existential and interconnected threats of climate change and biodiversity loss, the nature positive target is gaining attraction. Aimed at ending and reversing nature loss, it emphasises the need for a societal transformation to actively enhance ecosystems through human activities. Proponents argue that existing net-zero targets will not suffice to reach global climate goals if they are not coupled with nature-positive actions. Widespread efforts towards a nature positive future would inspire new business models and approaches to product and service development. However, the lack of standardised metrics still presents challenges and risks misuse of the concept.

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